

Intelligent Design: Reasonable, Rational, and Right

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***The information contained in this essay represents the opinions of the author.**

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Weernher von Braun once emphatically declared that “it was [his] experiences with science that led [him] to God.” By this, von Braun was asserting that in studying and learning about the discipline of science, he came to know a plausible, real, and powerful God. While he has drawn criticisms from some groups, his statement is actually rooted in truth. The study of science indeed has the potential to help one comprehend the nature of God more fully.

Although Naturalists contend that life began chemically, arising from nonliving material without an omnipotent creator, scientific logic refutes this. For one, this natural design, known as chemical evolution, would require abiogenesis, which has mathematically been proven impossible. Moreover, their claims of experiments that allude to the accuracy of the Naturalistic Theory are a clear overstatement of the results’ probative value. Furthermore, life is composed of more than just physical reality, containing intangible, unmeasurable elements that are just as real as the tangible. In addition, the occurrence of supernatural events, which require divine intervention to take place, stand as proof of an intelligent designer. When taken as a whole, the body of evidence through the use of mathematics, the application of logic, and the observation of supernatural events occurring today, makes a most compelling case for Intelligent Design.

The theory of chemical evolution proposes that simple chemicals on a prebiotic earth, slowly and gradually assembled into more complex molecular systems (Rosevear, 1999). Further asserted is that the organic building blocks of life making up these systems were created when inorganic materials came together resulting in the first functional cell (Could Chemical Evolution Produce DNA?, 2019). This however is contradicted mathematically. A bacterium which shows this is Mycoplasma Genitalium. The simplest bacteria in the world, it is composed of 483 genes (Balasubramanian et al, 2000). Hence, the probability of their randomly assembling over time would be calculated by the formula $\frac{1}{483!}$. In simplified terms this means

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1 chance in infinity ($1:\infty$), which is equal to zero (Story of Mathematics, 2024). A theoretical probability this low is as close to absolute impossibility one can get mathematically without being able to observe the event. Hence, the conclusion is that the first living cells would never have formed from nonlife. Since matter has two states, living and nonliving, we may rightly deduce that the original cause of life was a living cause.

Additionally, while the atheistic community claims that their findings are backed up by scale model experimental results, there are a number of facts that call this into question. In a 2009, anonymous study, 2% of scientists admitted to having falsified research data at least once, and 34% admitted to other forms of result manipulation (Fanelli, 2009). At first glance the first statistic appears to be small. However, when applying this to the general population, and considering that the number of scientists in the world is estimated to be at least 8 million, that's a lot of people, as 2% of 8 million is 160,000. Even scarier is the fact that 34% of 8 million people is 2,720,000 people, meaning that there is likely much more result manipulation happening in scientific studies than we are able to detect or know of reasonably.

An experiment hailed by the atheistic community as proof that life could have begun naturally without the need for a divine creator is the Urey Miller Experiment. In this experiment, conducted in 1952, Drs. Miller and Urey conducted an experiment in which gasses were trapped in a glass enclosure, supposedly replicating the earliest atmospheric conditions on Earth. A spark was then passed through this mixture to mimic lightning and amino acids were formed, which are the building blocks of life. However, three critical facts were omitted from this experiment : 1.) 98% of what the experiment created is poisonous to life; 2.) The atmosphere utilized did not accurately represent early atmospheric conditions; 3.) When Miller repeated the experiment in 1982, using the correct gasses, it failed to materialize. (Bromfield, 2024)

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Additionally, According to Bracewell (2021) & Brooks (2014), the following facts demonstrate the lack of probative value in this experiment. 1.) The concentrations of methane and ammonia were carefully selected to ensure the production of organic molecules. 2.) There is no evidence to suggest the Earth's atmosphere was so characterized. 3.) There is no evidence to indicate the Earth's early atmosphere was reducing. 4.) There is, however, considerable evidence to suggest the Earth had an oxidizing atmosphere during most, if not all, of its history. 5.) A methane-ammonia-reducing atmosphere would be fatal to life-forms. 6.) The simulation of lightning by mild spark discharges is unrealistic. Actual lightning would have destroyed any organics that may have been present. 7.) The molecules produced in the Miller-Urey apparatus would react detrimentally to life forms that were trying to evolve. Here, the logical conclusion is that chemically, what was produced in the Miller Urey Experiment would destroy all hope of producing life. Ultimately, the Miller Urey Experiment did not confirm the Naturalistic Theory of the Origin of Life, it debunked it. Hence, by default, the only plausible theory is Intelligent Design.

Another supporting point for Intelligent Design is that science restricts itself to that which is observable, measurable and quantifiable. However, this alone is insufficient to explain the human experience. Instead, those elements we cannot measure or perceive with our five senses along with that which is tangible tell the entire story. For example, if everyone in a room were asked to imagine a random picture in their minds and not tell anyone what it was, who would be able to tell anything about the mental picture, its shape, its dimensions, its colors, etc? Yet, common experience proves that although we cannot observe, measure, or quantify the specifics of the mental picture in somebody else's mind, we nonetheless believe it is real. While some would argue that we can measure brainwave activity, would that alone tell us the aforementioned

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characteristics of the picture? It certainly would not. Our belief in its reality although we cannot perceive it with any of our five senses is having had a common experience. Can the atheist then say that there is no way spiritual life, with the ability to contradict natural laws and act with intentionality exists? Does our inability to perceive it with our five senses negate the possibility of its presence? Is the absence of what they term evidence truly evidence of absence?

Perhaps the most persuasive testament to the presence of an omnipotent creator and the existence of the supernatural, comes from the case of 18-month-old Lily Groesbeck. Her mother, Lynn Jennifer Groesbeck was killed instantly when her car crashed into a river. Baby Lily was suspended upside down over frigid water for 14 hours. When the officers arrived, a voice was heard calling for help from inside the wreckage (Bucktin, 2016). By all natural laws, this cannot happen as Lynn was dead and her 18-month-old daughter unconscious. Still, the voice was heard and scientists today cannot explain it. Events that defy all natural laws have only one explanation, supernatural. This reveals to us more about the nature of the creator whom we as theists refer to as God. Via this revelation, God showed a characteristic some do not believe exists, omnipotence.

In conclusion, between the two competing theories of the origin of life, Natural Design and Intelligent Design, the evidence clearly demonstrates a case for the latter. Looking objectively at the evidence, the chance of even a simple bacteria evolving randomly from inorganic matter over a period of time is calculated at 1 in infinity, which is as close to 0% as one can get using theoretical probability for an event that cannot be observed. Adding to the probative nature of this calculation is the fact that although the use of this model gives the light most favorable to the Naturalistic Argument by assuming it to be a real possibility, it still shows essentially a zero probability of being true. Additionally, the use of experimental results from

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the Urey Miller experiment are used as the basis for the chemical evolution theory. Bracewell (2021) and Brooks (2014) however have shown using indisputable facts why the use of the Urey Miller Experiment to explain the origin of life is not feasible and its probative value accomplishes the opposite of what Naturalists claim. The interpretation of scientific evidence does not preclude us from using common sense; and the origin of life cannot be explained by an experiment that, if accurate, would have killed life before it began. Finally, the supernatural occurrence of a voice from inside a wreckage alerting, despite the fact that the sole occupants were dead and unconscious is indisputable proof of the truth of spiritual life. Atheists argue that many seemingly miraculous events do not require God to be plausible. Can the same be said for this event? Clearly it cannot. This divine intervention required God. It also continues to baffle scientists because all natural laws are defied. Taken as a whole, this body of evidence is powerful proof, albeit circumstantial, that God is real.

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